
E-MAIL BASED LIBRARY SERVICES: AN OVERVIEW

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Abstract:

In today's modern age there is an explosion of information. Libraries are trying to reach the correct information in the said information to the readers in minimum time. The first word that comes to mind when we think of modern technology is e-mail. In today's fast paced era where everyone wants to do everything quickly, e-mail is being used more and more to communicate information. An e-mail has become an important part of daily life. Due to the quality of email, today email is being used to provide online services from libraries. In today's age, a review has been made of what online facilities can be provided to the readers based on email.

Keywords: *E-mail, Library Services, e-mail history, Advantage e-mail, limitation of e-mail.*

Introduction:

The library is an ancient social Santha and has a long history. And it parallels human culture. Readers and librarians are the three major components of a library. The nature of the library changed over time. Library Architecture, Library Administration, Interlibrary Cooperation and International Library Association etc. factors are considered in modern libraries. These important factors are the type and function of the library.

In ancient times, papyrus and leather books were written in the library. And before that, manuscripts and later printed books were added. If we consider a modern library, a library includes periodicals, documents, manuscripts, maps, photographs, sculptures, inscriptions, coins, tickets, photographs,

printed tapes, microfilms, micrographs, photos, clippings, etc. A variety of audio-visual knowledge materials are stored. In ancient times it was only the job of the librarian to protect rare books but due to the change in the nature of the library in the modern era, how can the knowledge be spread in the society by allowing the readers to use the books more and more, how can the curiosity and needs of the readers be met promptly by treating them with affection? The librarian always proves to be the key element of today's library, by guiding the inquisitors in the right way, how to impart knowledge, entertainment as well as the sense of citizenship and culture, how to enrich their personality. Today's era is completely made up of online technology. In this age of modern technology there is not a single

person who is not connected with internet, computer and mobile. In this age of internet, almost all of us must have heard the word e-mail. Many people use e-mail to send messages.

What is e-mail id?

E-mail stands for electronic mail and is a form of digital message. Which a user uses to communicate with another user E-mail is a way to stay in touch with family and friends text, photo news in this e-mail or any other document may also be there. A network that can be sent to a specific person or any person. Simply put, E-mail is the process of sending a letter from one computer to another in the same way we send a letter by post.

E-mail is used in home office, school, college, court, industry, bank or any government or private office. An e-mail has become the most popular form of communication in today's digital age

E-mail History:

Ray Tomlinson invented the E-mail. The history of e-mail service goes back to ARPANET in 1971 when Ray developed the electronic mail system. In 1972, the world's first e-mail was sent from computer to computer. Ray Tomlinson sent that e-mail to himself as a test e-mail message under the system of file transfer protocol (FTP) in which he wrote the text QWERTYUIOP. There are two methods to create an e-mail smartphone, computer or laptop.

Email based Library Services:

In today's computerized age, information is growing at a tremendous speed. Libraries are working together when it is not possible for all libraries to purchase or preserve all collections. Libraries are using new technologies to

make the collection available to the readers in the shortest possible time. When it comes to technology, the first thing that comes to mind is email. Today some library services are provided by the library on the basis of email. Some of the library services are as follows:

- a. Resources sharing service
- b. Reference service
- c. Document delivery service
- d. Email alert service
- e. Ask a librarian

a. Resources Sharing Service :

Due to the current increasing modernization and computerization, information is being generated on a huge scale. In a situation where the needs of the readers are constantly changing, there are difficulties in providing all the information to the readers coming to the library. But it is the work of the library to make the information available to the readers. As a solution to this, the concept of resource sharing came forward. Today, many libraries provide the following services on the basis of e-mail. Inter-library loan, cooperative acquisition, centralized processing of library collection, shared cataloguing, sharing of bibliographical data, exchange of library expertise and personnel and etc.

b. Reference Service :

The reference service was defined by Dr. S.R Ranganathan, as "Reference service is a personal service to each reader in helping him to find the documents answering his interest at the moment pin pointedly, exhaustively and expeditiously". Library information is recorded in various documents. E.g. Books, journals, reports, research papers, standards, patents etc. The reader faces difficulties in finding the exact

information he needs in the shortest possible time because of the incomplete knowledge of information seeking or what can be called information explosion. The aim of the library should be to provide the information that the reader wants. A reference service provides personal assistance to the reader. We can provide this service very well through e-mail.

c. Document Delivery Service:

A good example of how a reader can make better use of his time in today's fast paced age is document delivery services. This service provided by the library helps to fulfil the work of the reader. If the reader requests the said facility, the service is provided to him in physical or electronic form at the address of the reader. But in course of time this facility is provided through e-mail. The said information is given in soft copy through e-mail. Hence accurate information is available to the reader in minimum time.

d. Email Alert Service :

The use of computers in libraries has increased today due to the use of information and technology. Computerization has led to automation of almost all libraries. This e-mail alert service is provided under books circulation e. g. book taken information, information about when to return books, new book catalogues in the library, library notices, etc. The effect of the said service is good on both the readers and the library.

e. Ask a Librarian Service :

This service is important for the readers as it is used to solve many problems that the readers face while searching for information. Readers can

send their problems through this e-mail. The librarian responds within twenty four hours excluding holidays. Such services include the following questions :

1. Availability of library materials
2. Inquiring about library services
3. Information about catalog or online database usage

Advantage email based Library Services:

- E-mail library service is a secure and reliable tool. Login ID and password are required to open the e-mail. E-mail can be opened only with correct e-mail id and password.
- E-mail library service is a popular free service in the world.
- One of the most important advantages of e-mail library service is that it is a powerful tool that can be used anywhere in the world.
- Not only can we send e-mails through words, but we can also send photos, important documents, videos, etc.
- E-mail provides a record of all your communications. You have all the information about who you communicated with and what they replied to. We can view that information at any time. We can also print it out. They remain saved in your e-mail until you delete them yourself.

Limitations of email based Library Services:

- An Internet connection is required to send or receive e-mail.
- There is a limitation that cannot send large files in e-mail.

- Cannot send .exe files in e-mail.

Conclusion:

Today, the use of information and communication technology in libraries is increasing. Libraries are using new technology to provide accurate information to all sections of the society in minimum time. Today, the use of email is increasing all over the world. One of the most convenient means of providing library information to the community is e-mail. The use of e-mail based library services is found to have a positive impact on the library and the readers. E-mail can be said to be an important means of information communication if we ignore some minor limitations.

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